

SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT IN TEACHER DEVELOPMENT: UTILIZING PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AS A TRAINING ASSIGNMENT STRATEGY

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Abstract: Education is the main foundation in shaping a thriving and sustainable society. The quality of instruction provided by teachers is a key factor in achieving optimal educational goals. This article explores the concept of social engagement in the context of teacher development with a focus on the utilization of performance appraisal as a strategy for determining training. Through a sociology of education perspective, this research aims to explore the complex relationship between social factors, interactions within the educational environment and the improvement of teacher professionalism. By integrating these concepts, this article details how teacher performance appraisals can be an effective foundation in establishing relevant training programs that positively impact their professional development. The method used in this study is Literature Review by reviewing three literatures related to research inclusion. Article searches were conducted through lens.org and google scholar. From the results of the study, it was found that the utilization of teacher performance appraisals was only utilized on the needs for payroll and promotion, not yet to the stage of determining the most needed training for teachers related to the results of performance appraisals. further evaluation of power dynamics, social interactions, and teacher participation in the performance appraisal process and determination of training is needed. This is important to achieve a more holistic and contextual approach to human resource management in education.

Keywords: social engagement, teacher development, performance appraisal, teacher performance, teacher training

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Introduction

The social involvement of each individual in a group has an impact on their development, the higher the score of social involvement in the group, the higher the score of the level of self-adjustment ability that occurs in the self. Performance appraisal is needed in every field including education. The role of the teacher in carrying out tasks also does not escape the target of performance appraisal. Performance appraisals are generally used to determine allowances and payroll [1], as well as data-based reports such as in research conducted by Lembong et al. which shows that application-based performance appraisals show positive results [2].

In general, teacher performance competency standards are grouped into 4 competencies, namely pedagogical competence, personality competence, social competence and professional competence, this is in accordance with the Minister of Education Regulation number 16 of 2007 which contains standards for academic qualifications and teacher competencies.

According to Aswaruddin in his research, teacher performance can be measured with certain criteria [3], this measurement has of course been adjusted to the teacher qualification standards.

In supporting the improvement of teacher competence, there are various kinds of training that can be carried out by teachers. Before the pandemic, every training that teachers had to participate in was more of a direct or face-to-face activity. However, since the pandemic, teacher training has been carried out online. Both the government, educational institutions, teacher organizations and the private sector have provided various kinds of training related to teacher competency development. However, from the many trainings offered, it is not uncommon for teachers to choose the training they attend without considering their needs. It is not uncommon for teachers to attend training just because it is "mandatory".

Previous research and research recommendations where educator competency training has a major influence on teacher performance in educating. In line with research conducted by Andriyuan, that PKG or Teacher Performance Assessment is a coaching and development activity with continuous feedback [4]. In research on the teacher community at SMA 2 Gedong Tataan shows that PKG training has been successfully carried out but there is no continuation of the program after PKG is carried out [5]. Given the gaps in research findings it is imperative to investigate the utilization of performance appraisal in the determination of teacher competency improvement through teacher training.

Methods

This research uses the literature review method or literature research as its type and method. This research uses the Literature Review (LR) method. Starting with a methodical literature search of research articles or articles on the same topic, this research includes a review of various published reports or research articles. In the first step, the researchers used Lens.org to conduct a literature search using the keywords "performance appraisal" "teacher performance" and "teacher training" between 2020 and 2022, resulting in the discovery of 28 journals. The researchers then moved on to analysis to determine the quality of the articles or journals after completing the inclusion and exclusion procedures, resulting in the following 3 articles to be synthesized.

Results and Discussion

There were three articles that met the inclusion criteria, and all of them met the researcher's objectives for the literature search. Related to Utilization of performance appraisal in teacher training determination. The three journals identified were research journals. Peer-reviewed journals are only journals that publish research conducted in schools because questions and topics relevant to teacher performance, performance appraisal and teacher training, have not been studied extensively.

Based on the three journals to be examined and providing clear and comprehensive information on research methods, location, sample size, design and results. The three journals used in the literature review are summarized in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1 Previous Research

Author Year	Research Title	Place Research	Design Research	Research Results
Suwatri, 2022	Application Training	SMA N 2 Gedong Tataan	Method qualitativevia	Based on outcome

	Performance Assessment Teacher (PKG) Using Excel-based Application Excel for Teacher Community in senior high school			observation, interviews and documentation	evaluation training, data obtained 80% of teachers have mastered about the training performance assessment training teacher performance appraisal training well and satisfactory, while 20% other teachers must be given assistance. Furthermore A team was formed to performance assessment team teacher performance appraisal team from senior teachers who given the task to conduct assessment the performance of junior teachers assisting teachers to improve shortcomings, improve competence and quality performance towards becoming a teacher who is professional
Musfira, 2022	Influence Training Competence Educators Education Inclusive On the Performance of Teacher Performance in	SMPN Bandung	30	Method survey method that using approach quantitative approach. Data obtained through literature study, literature study, field study field study through	Implementation Training Competence Educators Education already running quite well, explanation of material

	Organizing an Education Inclusive Education Smpn Bandung	30	observation, interviews, and dissemination of questionnaire	training material that not yet explained and at the end activity was not done evaluation training, Teacher Performance in Organizing Education Inclusive Education at SMPN 30 Bandung is good enough good, the influence of Training Competence Educators Education on Teacher Performance in Organizing Education Inclusive Education at SMPN 30 Bandung amounted to 39.5% which means has influence is quite high.
Andriyuan 2018	Improving Professionalism Teaching Teacher Via Implementation of Performance Assessment Teacher Performance Appraisal at Smp Negeri 5 Singingi District Kuantan Singingi	SMP NEGERI 5 Singingi Kabupaten Kuantan Singingi	Qualitative, research field (field research)	Research results obtained that the efforts of the Head of SMP Negeri 5 Singingi Regency Kuantan Singingi about improving professionalism teacher professionalism that has been conducted through: 1) Coaching to teachers in preparing

Plan lesson plans;
 2) Monitoring teachers in implementing learning; 3) Supervising the running of programs activities education; 4) Checking state and integrity facilities of SMP 5 Singingi Kuantan Singingi Regency as a support for achievement of students students' achievements; and 4)Evaluating through briefings and meetings program education program meetings in an effort to improve professionalism teacher teaching in class

The three journals reviewed two of which are qualitative research journals and one is a quantitative journal. The research conducted by Suwatri, et al on teachers at SMAN 2 Gedong Tatanan totaling 22 teachers began with the implementation of PKG or Teacher Performance Appraisal which is still running slowly because it is done manually, therefore to improve teacher competence and improve the implementation of PKG activities, an excel training on application-based PKG implementation was held. Before planning the training, a needs analysis was conducted with the results that 75% of teachers did not understand about teacher performance appraisal and 100% of teachers had the desire to attend teacher performance training.

This training uses an excel-based application where the assessment instrument consists of inputting school data, teacher and assessor data, teacher performance assessment, teacher and student respondents, parent respondents, teacher attendance, and printing assessment results. From the observation of activities for three days, it appears that 100% of participants are enthusiastic in participating in the activities. From the results of interviews with 22 teachers as respondents with five questions and four answer options, namely strongly agree (ss), agree (s), disagree (ks), and disagree (ts), the average respondent answered strongly agree and agree. After the teacher performance assessment process is carried out, a mapping of each instrument listed in the teacher performance assessment should be carried out. The goal is to find out the weaknesses that still occur in most

teachers to be used as a school reference in the development of each teacher's PKB. The training runs for three days with the final result that 80% have mastered the excel application-based performance appraisal and 20% with assistance.

The results of further research conducted by Ratna Shella et al at SMPN 30 Bandung on the analysis of needs related to the competency training of educators and inclusive education. Bandung on analyzing the needs related to the competency training of educators and inclusive education from the results of respondents assessing the training conducted has not been as needed. Based on the results of interviews, respondents agreed with the purpose of training to increase knowledge about inclusive education and improve services in education. Based on the results of the calculation, it is known that the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between training and teacher performance is 0.628 with a strong correlation level. The coefficient of determination is 39.5%. The coefficient of determination is 39.5%, which means that 39.5% of teacher performance is determined by training and 60.5% is influenced by other variables not examined. With that, it can be seen that the effect of Inclusive Education Educator Competency Training on Teacher Performance in Organizing Inclusive Education at SMPN 30 Bandung is 39.5% with a fairly high category.

Another study conducted by Andriyuan at SMPN 1 Singingi, Kuantan Singingi Regency found that teacher performance appraisals generally function to assess teacher abilities and to calculate credit numbers in career development or functional position promotion. Based on the data obtained in the field, the teacher performance appraisal regarding teacher professionalism that occurs at SMP Negeri 5 Singingi Kuantan Singingi Regency is a fair teacher performance appraisal, where the teacher performance appraisal here tends to carry out actions that always absorb the aspirations of his subordinates, this is evident during the working meeting of SMP Negeri 5 Singingi Kuantan Singingi Regency, the teachers are directly involved in developing programs for the advancement of education.

Conclusion

Performance appraisals can be used to determine teacher training. According to the research conducted, from the findings obtained that the excel application-based teacher performance appraisal can support the implementation of performance appraisals more efficiently, a needs analysis process is carried out in determining teacher training to improve teacher abilities and be an improvement from the previous PKG results. The utilization of Teacher Performance Appraisal should be maximized in determining teacher training according to the development needs of each teacher. Further evaluation of power dynamics, social interactions, and teacher participation in the performance appraisal process and training determination is needed. This is important to achieve a more holistic and contextual approach to human resource management in education.

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